

SHAHRUKH MIRZA'S COURT LIBRARY

Muhridin Kholov Hamrali ugli

Independent researcher, Faculty of History,

Fergana State University

xolovmuhridin41@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20306271>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08th May 2026Accepted: 09th May 2026Online: 20th May 2026

KEYWORDS

Shahrukh Mirza, Sultan Barsbay, Amir Chaqmoq, Herat, yasa, kaba-push.

ABSTRACT

The Timurid period is considered one of the most significant eras in the history of Central Asia in terms of the development of science, culture, and enlightenment. During this period, rulers acted as patrons of scholars and placed great emphasis on the development of libraries, madrasas, and scientific centers. One of such enlightened rulers was Shahrukh Mirza, whose court library was regarded as one of the richest and most renowned intellectual centers of its time

Introduction: Shahrukh Mirza ruled the regions of Khorasan and Movarounnahr in the 15th century. Alongside governing the state, he paid great attention to the development of science and culture. During his reign, Herat in particular became a major scientific and cultural center. After Shahrukh Mirza transferred the capital to Herat, extensive construction works were carried out in the city. Madrasas, mosques, gardens, and libraries were built. In a short period, Herat became one of the most developed intellectual centers of the East. The court library was located at the heart of this scholarly environment and preserved thousands of manuscripts on various fields of knowledge. It also served as a workplace for scholars, historians, calligraphers, and artists.

The establishment of the court library made it one of the most important intellectual institutions within the royal palace. Shahrukh Mirza's wife, Gawharshad Begum, also supported its activities as a patron of science and culture. The historical significance of the library lies in its role as one of the key symbols of scientific progress during the Timurid era. Through this library, many scientific works were preserved and transmitted to later generations. Its activities also had a significant influence on the scientific development of the time of Mirza Ulugh Beg. Timurid libraries occupy a special place in history as important centers of the Eastern Renaissance.

According to M. Ashrafi, the court library established by Shahrukh Mirza in Herat was regarded as a major intellectual center.[1:23]. Scholars collected books from various branches of science, and particular attention was given to the translation and copying of manuscripts. According to Shamil Yüksel, in 1428 the Mamluk ruler of Egypt, Sultan Barsbay (Baybars), requested a rare manuscript of Imam al-Bukhari's *Al-Jami' al-Sahih* from this library.[2:30].

In particular, the Egyptian ruler Chaqmoqbek sent his envoy Chichaktuko (Jijikbuqo) to Herat in 1439. According to Khondamir, they requested several books from the Sultan.[3:438]. In "Habib al-Siyar," the works of Abu Mansur Maturidi, Fakhr al-Razi's *Tafsir al-Kabir*, a commentary on Khwaja Mas'ud Bukhari's work, Mavlon Alauddin's *Sharh-i Kashshaf*, and *Sharh-i Rawza dar Madhhab-i Shafi'i* are mentioned. Abdurazzaq Samarqandi writes: "Sultan Chaqmoq requested five books from the library of the Sultan of horizons, Shahrukh, hoping that His Majesty would grant the works of Shaykh Abu Mansur Maturidi's *Ta'wilat Ahl al-Sunnah*, Imam Fakhruddin's *Tafsir al-Kabir*, *Sharh-i Talkhis Jami'*, Mavlon Alauddin Pahlavan's *Sharh-i Kashshaf...*"[4:87]. Although the reports differ slightly, both sources indicate that the name of the fifth book is not mentioned.

It is also noted that the original manuscripts were not sent; instead, copies were made on the order of Shahrukh Mirza. However, there is no information about which calligrapher produced these copies. This demonstrates that he highly valued books, appreciated their importance, and protected the cultural heritage of his country. Although this diplomatic mission had certain political objectives, it also reflects the existence of cultural and educational relations between the two countries. V.V. Bartold notes that during Shahrukh Mirza's reign, science flourished in Herat, and he was well acquainted with Qur'anic recitation, tafsir, hadith, and kalam, and began replacing the laws of "yasa" with Islamic regulations.[5:161–162].

He had long wished to cover the Kaaba with a "joma" or "kaba-push," but since this could not be done without the permission of the rulers of Egypt, he sent envoys in 1439–1440.[4:167–168]. According to Khondamir, in 1443 Shahrukh Mirza sent envoys led by Sayyid Muhammad Zamzami to Sultan Chaqmoq and obtained permission to prepare the "kaba-push." This task was entrusted to Shaykh Nuriddin Muhammad al-Murshidi and Mavloni Shamsuddin Muhammad al-Abhari.[3:444–445]. In "Tarikh-i Jadid-i Yazd," it is stated that, by order of Shahrukh Mirza, the "kaba-push" was produced in a weaving workshop in Yazd and brought to Herat. This workshop had been established by Amir Chaqmoq, one of Shahrukh Mirza's close associates. The head of the city weavers was Mavloni Faraj.

Mu'iniddin Isfzoriy, in his work, discusses the outbreak of a contagious disease that spread in Herat and its surrounding areas during the reign of Shahrukh Mirza in 1435, referring to it as "plague (vabo-toun)." Fasih Khavofi provides a detailed account of this epidemic, noting that more than 10,000 people died, including representatives of science, culture, and religious scholars. As a result, many intellectuals migrated to other regions, which inevitably affected the scientific and literary processes of the time.

With the patronage of Shahrukh Mirza, several significant historical works were produced and rare sources were recopied. For instance, Abd al-Razzaq Samarqandi wrote a commentary on Qazi Azduddin's Arabic language and grammar work "Risala-yi Azudiyya" and dedicated it to Shahrukh Mirza [4:14]. The above information indicates Shahrukh Mirza's strong interest in fields such as history and geography. Moreover, during his reign, linguistics and literary studies flourished, and the tradition of "khamsataynlik" became widespread among scholars.

On this subject, Mirza Muhammad Haydar writes: "During the time of Mirza Shahrukh, in all of Movarounnahr and Khurasan there were five individuals whom the scholars called 'Khamsa-yi Mustajarra.' The first was Hazrat Mawlana Abd al-Rahman Jami, the second Mawlana Dawud Hori, the third Mawlana Shaykh Husayn Muhtasib, the fourth Mawlana Shamsuddin Bahrobodi, and the fifth Mawlana Burhaniddin..." [6:270]. This account shows that these five scholars gained fame under the collective name "Khamsa-yi Mustajarra" in Movarounnahr and Khurasan.

Conclusion. Shahrukh Mirza's palace library served as a major center of enlightenment in the 15th century, contributing significantly to the development of science and culture. The library was not only a place for preserving books but also an intellectual hub where scholars and creative thinkers gathered. Thanks to Shahrukh Mirza's patronage of science, a rich cultural heritage was created during the Timurid era, which continues to retain its significance today.

References:

1. Ashrafiy M. *The Miniature Art of the Samarqand Period of Timur and Ulugh Beg.* – p. 23.
2. Şamil Yüksel. *Religion–State Relations in the Timurids.* – p. 30.
3. Khondamir. *Habib al-Siyar.* – p. 438.
4. Abd al-Razzaq Samarqandi. *Matla' al-Sa'dayn wa Majma' al-Bahrayn.* – p. 87.
5. V.V. Bartold. *An Outline of the History of Semirechye.* – pp. 161–162.
6. Mirza Muhammad Haidar. *Tarikh-i Rashidi.* – p. 270.